

USING THE SPIRITUAL HERITAGE LEFT BY EASTERN THINKERS IN EDUCATING YOUNG PEOPLE IN THE SPIRIT OF HONESTY AND THREENESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111596>

Abstract: The article clearly states that the themes of honesty, truthfulness, hard work, correctness, honesty, and religion are expressed in folk masterpieces, and they are preserved in human intelligence, kindness, and the language of the people.

Key words: Folk masterpieces, honesty, truthfulness, hard work, correctness, honesty, piety, intelligence, kindness.

The place of our great poet and thinker Alisher Navoi and his services in the spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, in the development of its culture on an international scale, are incomparable. Alisher Navoi's scientific heritage is so rich and wide-ranging that many valuable ideas on the issues of honesty and thrift are expressed in it. The thinker's views on commerce and thrift are described in his work "Mahbub ul-Qulub". In this work, Navoi curses the treacherous, self-serving, greedy, moneylenders who buy cheap, sell high, and cause damage. In the work, he encourages people to be polite, humble, humble, shy, honest, honest, pure, able to restrain their ego, and glorifies humanity at a high level. In the following sermons, A.Navoi talks about self-restraint, arrogance and conceit characteristic of ignorant people, and unnecessary extravagance is not generosity. "He who falls into the chain of desire stops only at the destination of passion. No one wants to be sad and he doesn't want to torture his ego." In the work, greed is shown as the worst quality in a person, and he is disgusted with it. "A stingy person takes great pains to preserve his wealth. And the envious person cannot live peacefully because of his mischievous behavior. One will suffer from the pain he gave himself, and the other will suffer from his own actions.

From the following points, it can be concluded that they will achieve prosperity as a result of treating all the things acquired through labor with thrift and passion, not allowing extravagance. "There is a reason for everything. But the cause of poverty is waste. Waste is not only the consumption of wealth, but also waste in food, one's actions, speech, waste deceives the body, hurts the breath, escapes the mind and kills the living, don't you see, the life of the lamp is with oil. If you put too much oil, the oil will go to the top of the lamp and put out the

lamp, and the oil was the reason for the lamp to burn, and because of waste, it caused its death..." The following points are made about the correctness of trade and trade: "There are two types of trade, both are dangerous: one is trading, the other is traveling. I am typical of friendly comrades (residents), they buy cheap goods with a taste for profit. In this case, the property is at risk, and a brave and far-sighted person should take the property with the hope of profit. Therefore, by all means, a merchant should be careful with his property and body, not be careless. At the same time, (the merchant) should make a habit of trust and honesty, should not harm others for his own benefit, and deal with a person who is subordinate to him. He can deal with such a great person that he is pious and benevolent, and avoids a swindler. He does not know the good and the bad of wealth and does not deal with people who have little wealth. (If he deals with such a person), he should not take advantage of it, so that the friendship between the two of them is not destroyed.

The next admonition urges people not to betray someone's rights, to be honest and kind in business. "Don't tell a lie in trade, telling a lie during trade is a very bad verb between a non-believer and a Muslim. Don't let anything go until you sell it and don't be ashamed in dealings, as the wise say, shame creates many hopes and dreams. But don't be too ungrateful and lewd, (it) won't help. They said that the essence of trade is stewardship and kindness. Because these are the reasons for keeping the property alive. The following advice is given to be polite in dealings, to keep promises, not to be unfaithful, and to stay out of the country's sight if a person betrays once: "O child, avoid treachery, because the one who betrays once will not be trusted by anyone. Cultivate righteousness, for righteousness is the best deed. Be polite in dealings and don't make promises to someone, and if you make a promise, don't go against it.

Do not lie to the buyer, tell the truth. Be careful in dealings, when you give someone a document or when you receive a document. The following story tells about the fact that a person who betrays someone's rights will ultimately suffer. "I heard that one man had too many sheep. He had an honest and unfaithful shepherd. Every day he milked the sheep and brought the milk to the owner of the sheep. The owner of the sheep would add half of water to the milk and ask the shepherd to buy it. The shepherd advised him: "O master, do not betray the Muslims, because you will harm yourself." That person did not listen to the advice of the shepherd and continued to betray. One night, during the spring, he put the sheep in the place where the flood flows, and he himself went up to a height and slept. Union, it rained a lot and the flood came and washed away the

sheep and all the sheep died. On the second day, the shepherd came to the city. The owner of the sheep said to him: "Why didn't you bring milk today?" Shepherd: "O master, I told you not to add water to milk, you didn't listen to me at all. "All the water you added to the milk the other night collected and flowed like a flood and drowned the sheep," he answered. Another story advises not to betray a deposit: "I heard that a man left his house in the dark at dawn and wanted to go to the bathroom.

He said to one of his friends: "Come with me to the bathroom!" He said: "I will go with you, but I will not go to the bath, because I have something important to do." He and his companion went towards the bathroom. He went to the place where the two boys had gone and went to the bathroom without informing his friend. His companion used to go to the bathroom alone and thought that he would come with his friend. Union, a thief kept following the man, he thought he was a friend, and he had a hundred pieces of gold in his pocket. At the door of the bathroom, he took the gold out of his pocket and gave it to the thief without recognizing him in the dark of the night and said: "O brother, let this gold stay with you until I get out of the bath, and after I get out of the bath, you will hand it over to me."

The thief took the gold and sat there. The man left the bathroom and put on his clothes. The thief called after him and said: "You young man, come and take your gold from me. Today, I quit my job to save your deposit." The man said: "Who are you, what kind of gold is this gold?" The thief said: "I am a thief, this gold is the gold you gave me." The man said, "If you are a thief, why didn't you take this gold?" The thief said: "Even if I had a thousand gold, I would have taken it from you without thinking, but you entrusted this gold to me." Betraying a deposit is not a sign of youth. In the past, the knowledge that serves to study the economic foundations of life was taught in families by parents and in schools and madrasas through artistic, scientific and historical sources. In these sources, all major and minor issues encountered in everyday life, be it in the economic, financial, social-administrative, or jurisprudential spheres, are expressed and revealed in a way that is understandable on a vital basis. The themes of honesty, truthfulness, hard work, correctness, honesty, religion are expressed in folk masterpieces. They express human intelligence, compassion and his great creative power through very impressive artistic means. They have been passed down from generation to generation for hundreds of years and have been preserved in the language of the people. The use of examples of folklore and

written literature in improving students' economic knowledge gives positive results.

References:

1. Mikhail Bakhtin. Forms of time and chronotope in the novel. T. "Akademnashr", 2015. Page 121
2. Abdullah Qadiri. Selected works. "Sharq" publishing house. 2014 Page 294.

